

EXTERNAL ENGAGEMENTS AND INITIATIVES OF PUBLIC SCHOOLS IN SUPPORT TO LOCAL INDIGENOUS COMMUNITIES

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ABSTRACT

The main thrust of the study was to identify the external engagements and initiatives of public schools in support to local indigenous communities for the School Year 2023-2024. It also aimed to determine the main drivers of the external engagements and initiatives, challenges encountered by the public schools in the implementation of the external engagements and initiatives, and the needs expressed by the public schools in their initiatives to help the local indigenous communities. The relevant data on the external engagements and initiatives of public schools in support of the Eskaya indigenous local community were obtained from the school principals, head teachers, and school-in-charge in the selected elementary schools of Duero, Guindulman, Alicia, Pilar, Sierra Bullones, and Candijay, where IPEd implementing schools took place. The researcher utilized semi-structured researcher-made questions. The researcher also included face-to-face interviews to establish validity and reliability. Based on the data obtained, it was found that educational support, cultural preservation and promotion, community development, and environmental stewardship were the external engagement and initiatives undertaken by the public schools in support of indigenous cultural communities. The main drivers of external engagement and initiatives were the school principals/teachers/staff. Further, collaboration from BLGU/MLGU/NGOs were deemed significant for the full realization of the external engagements and initiatives. Challenges identified include financial constraint, insufficient knowledge of the Eskaya language and

cultural practices, and unavailability of up-to-date technology aided instructional materials are also the challenges faced by the main drivers in the external engagements and initiatives to the local indigenous communities. Financial support from BLGU/MLGU, professional development of IP teachers, and technology aided instructional materials were the identified needs of the public schools in the external engagements and initiatives to the local indigenous communities.

Keywords: *external engagements and initiatives of school heads, local indigenous communities, elementary public schools, challenges of school heads, needs of local indigenous communities*

INTRODUCTION

The right to education is recognized as a core component of sustainable development and a shared responsibility among global actors, as emphasized in the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (Bexell & Jönsson, 2017). It is a universal right that must be upheld for all individuals, regardless of language, culture, religion, economic status, social origin, or political beliefs. The United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP) regenerated the rights of Indigenous People, which covers the declaration's scope, applicability, and implication on national law on indigenous rights (Mansell, 2011; Newcomb, 2011; Wiessner, 2008).

Similarly, the right to education of IPs/Indigenous Cultural Communities (ICCs) is also promoted and protected in the Philippines. Numerous laws, statutes, and policies were forged to make education accessible to vulnerable groups such as the Indigenous Peoples (IPs). This indicates that the Philippines is aware of the needs of its marginalized communities and are creating policies that are responsive to it, especially in the aspect of social rights, with the right to education being among it.

On the other hand, external engagements and initiatives involve people or groups who have a high degree of influence or impact in the integrated strategy development and implementation of programs, as seen in the collaborative practices of the Business Council for Sustainable Development Zimbabwe (Muzamwese, 2024). In education, these would refer to the efforts and expertise extended by the institution to specific beneficiaries with the principle of reciprocity, where both parties can gain something beneficial for their organization. Further, the course of action has been evident in the Department of Education in which schools provide significant efforts to enrich the external organization or beneficiaries of the programs. Community engagement can lead to improved outcomes when key stakeholders, such as community members and organizations, are meaningfully involved in shaping programs and decision-making processes. Their participation enhances the relevance, quality, and sustainability of initiatives by ensuring that diverse perspectives and local needs are addressed (Martinez et al., 2018). External engagements between communities and institutions of government make community engagement not only desirable, but necessary and viable as it is likely

to lead to more equitable, sustainable public decisions and improve the livability of indigenous local communities.

With that, engagements and initiatives were extended by DepEd to address the challenges and cater the pressing needs of the marginalized indigenous cultural communities. Particularly, the researcher had initially observed several challenges in its implementation, including the budgetary constraint and limited access on up-to-date teaching and learning materials. Also, there were existing studies on indigenous cultural and identity preservation but less to no studies on the existing external engagements and initiatives of public schools. To verify and address the pressing challenges and needs in its implementation, the researcher was encouraged to focus on the external engagements and initiatives of public schools to the local indigenous communities.

In this study, the researcher focused on the province of Bohol, particularly in the towns of Duero, Sierra Bullones, Candijay, Pilar, and Alicia. These towns have several elementary schools where Indigenous People Education (IPEd) Program has been implemented, specifically the Eskaya Indigenous Cultural Community. The researcher was enthused to give emphasis in these schools as they were seen as significant fora in the enrichment of indigenous cultural communities with the engagements and initiatives they have provided to the local indigenous communities.

Research Questions

The main thrust of this research was to identify the external engagements and initiatives of public schools in support to local indigenous communities for the School Year 2023-2024. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What external engagements and initiatives are undertaken by the public schools to assist the indigenous communities?
2. Who are the main drivers of the school initiatives?
3. What are the challenges encountered by the public schools in these external engagements and initiatives?
4. What are the expressed needs of the public schools in their initiatives to help the local indigenous communities?
5. What plan of action can be proposed to enrich the local indigenous communities?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researcher utilized qualitative research design to determine the external engagements and initiatives undertaken by public school to the local indigenous community, Eskaya. This design is an inductive approach that sets out to obtain and analyze data using comparative analysis (Tie, et. al, 2019). The focus of the plan was to

develop categories and themes from grounded field data, and the data would be gathered through in-depth interviews.

Research Environment

The study was conducted at Taytay Elementary School in Duero, Bohol; Cantaub Elementary School in Sierra Bullones, Bohol; Biabas Elementary School, Tambis Elementary School, Bayong Elementary School, and Lombog Elementary School in Guindulman, Bohol; Cadapdapan Elementary School in Candijay, Bohol; Lundag Elementary School and Inaghuban Elementary School in Pilar, Bohol; Katipunan Annex Elementary School in Alicia, Bohol. The aforementioned elementary school in the respective towns of Bohol were Indigenous People Education (IPEd) implementing schools. These schools have consistently implemented the IPEd program initiated by the Department of Education; thus, it was deemed imperative to conduct the study in those locales where the external engagements and initiatives have taken place.

Research Respondents

The relevant data on the external engagements and initiatives of public schools in support of the Eskaya indigenous local community were obtained from the school principals, head teachers, and school-in-charge in the selected elementary schools of Duero, Guindulman, Alicia, Pilar, Sierra Bullones, and Candijay, where IPEd implementing schools took place.

Considerably, the respondents of this study were selected through purposive sampling method. The selection of the subject for this study followed the guidelines, to wit: the respondents have direct external engagements to the local indigenous community, one of the drivers of the external engagements and have taken initiative in support the Eskaya indigenous community.

Distribution of Respondents

Town	Name of School	Respondents Involved
Duero, Bohol	Taytay Elementary School	School Principals/Head Teachers/School-In-Charge
Sierra Bullones, Bohol	Cantaub Elementary School	
Guindulman, Bohol	Biabas Elementary School	
	Tambis Elementary School	
	Bayong Elementary School	
	Lombog Elementary School	
Candijay, Bohol	Cadapdapan Elementary School	
Pilar, Bohol	Lundag Elementary School	
	Inaghuban Elementary School	
Alicia, Bohol	Katipunan Annex Elementary School	
Total		10 Respondents

These informants were chosen because the researcher believed that they can significantly provide relevant data to address the objectives of the study. More importantly, all data collected from the respondents were treated with full confidentiality. Also, the names of the respondents were kept anonymously and the researcher made sure that identity was encrypted to secure the data of the respondents.

To validate the data on the external engagements and initiatives taken by the public school for the Eskaya indigenous community, data were obtained from the respondents, after which the data on the challenges and needs of the drivers and Eskaya indigenous community on the external engagements and initiatives have been determined and identified.

Research Instrument

The researcher utilized semi-structured researcher-made questions. The questions were tailor-fit to the objectives of the study. Considering that the study was qualitative in nature, the researcher included objective and subjective questions in which the respondents expounded their answers based on the question variables. In addition, the researcher also included face-to-face interviews to establish validity and reliability of the responses from the respondents. Also, the answers were recorded, given the approval of the respondents. Guide questions were provided as one of the attachments.

Research Procedure

A letter of permission was sent to the respective municipalities of the IPEd implementing schools, requesting for the permission and approval to conduct the study to its constituents, Eskaya indigenous community.

After the approval, a letter was addressed to the district supervisors and school principals to further ask for permission to conduct the study. Prior to the distribution of tool, the researcher secured first the signed Informed Consent and Assent as necessary documents prior to the conduct of the study. The researcher scheduled a time and date for the actual conduct of the study.

The gathering of data was done through interviews, then the researcher scheduled for an interview with the school principals, teachers/IPEd teachers. The interview was noted and recorded, and the information gathered was treated with the highest confidentiality. Answers provided by the respondents were transcribed and thematized for proper organization of ideas and better analysis.

The researcher assured that the research respondents' responses were treated with an adequate level of confidentiality. The research respondents' responses were also kept with full respect and privacy. The research respondents were given an Informed Consent Form, and the researcher has assured that the respondents have fully

understood the process of the research study prior to signing. The researcher also assured that complete anonymity in managing and discarding of the data. Further, the researcher also emphasized that they could stop answering at any point when they feel that their rights were violated. The contact details of the researcher were provided to ensure that the respondents can readily contact the researcher if there are queries after the data gathering. The whole process in the study was done with honesty and transparency.

RESULTS

The chapter presents analysis and interprets the data which are collected in connection with this study. The information pertains to the knowledge and experiences of respondents on external engagements and initiatives of public schools in support of local indigenous communities.

Table 1. External Engagements and Initiatives of Public Schools

Themes	Categories
1. Educational Support	Providing scholarships or financial aid for Indigenous students to access education and training
	Offering culturally relevant curriculum and teaching materials that incorporate Indigenous perspectives, languages, and traditions
	Establishing mentorship programs or tutoring services to support academic success and cultural identity development
2. Cultural Preservation and Promotion	Organizing cultural events or festivals to celebrate Indigenous heritage, traditions, and arts
	Collaborating with indigenous elders, knowledge keepers, and artists to share traditional knowledge, storytelling, and artistic practices
	Creating Indigenous language revitalization programs and resources to preserve and promote Indigenous languages
3. Community Development	Supporting community-led initiatives for economic development, such as entrepreneurship training and small business support

	Partnering with Indigenous organizations and community leaders to address social issues, promote health and wellness, and strengthen community resilience
	Facilitating access to community resources, including healthcare services, housing assistance, and legal support
4. Environmental Stewardship	Incorporating Indigenous perspectives on land stewardship, conservation, and sustainability into environmental education programs
	Collaborating with Indigenous communities on land management projects, wildlife conservation efforts, and traditional ecological knowledge sharing
	Engage families on life-long learning activities such as community clean-up and other related sustainable activities

As reflected in Table 1, four themes on external engagements and initiatives of public schools are identified by the researcher. Firstly, educational support refers to providing financial aids for indigenous students, incorporating culturally relevant curriculum and teaching materials, and establishing tutoring or mentoring to support cultural identity development of the indigenous learners. Based on the responses, several respondents said that teachers educate the learners about the IP language and culture with the use of different learning materials and teachers also integrate mentoring to academically help the academically struggling indigenous learners. Also, some respondents said that through education programs like IPEd and AGAK program, it helped the learners to pursue higher learners with the assistance received. Some respondents also said that improving access and outcomes of IP learners' scholarships and providing teachers with several vocational training could help in their professional and economic growth. This would mean that support to academic success of local indigenous communities is one of the engagements and initiatives extended by the public schools to capacitate the knowledge and skills of indigenous learners and teachers.

Secondly, cultural preservation and promotion is identified as another external engagement and initiatives of public schools. It refers to the main drivers' initiatives of organizing cultural events to celebrate indigenous traditions, collaborating with indigenous leaders to share artistic practices, and creating diverse indigenous programs to enrich the culture and identity of the indigenous community. Several respondents said that they encouraged pupils and teachers in attending and participating events in the community and they consistently host and attend IPEd events. Several respondents added that school principals and teachers actively engaged with the heads of the indigenous communities especially during occasions and activities related with Eskaya and tapped Eskaya elders who are equipped with teachings of Eskaya language to teach with the learners inside the school and activity engages during occasions, activities, and

celebrations related to Eskaya. Also, several respondents said that school heads and teachers, through cultural preservation projects like collaborating with the indigenous elders, helped to document and preserve languages, traditions and histories. These statements from the respondents would mean that school principals, teachers, and learners have been consistently supporting the cultural activities of local indigenous community.

Thirdly, community development which pertains to main drivers' efforts support the indigenous communities with entrepreneurial trainings, community resilience, health and wellness, address social issues, and other economic development initiatives. Several respondents said that they are conducting online survey, running community programs, conducting focus group discussion to identify the needs of the indigenous communities. Several respondents added that attending community events and meetings, taking time to explain to the local people on the significance and distinct identity of Eskaya ICC and how they can be valued are some of their efforts for the indigenous communities. They also added that teachers implement and educate the learners about the IKSP and culture and they conduct physical exercises to learners and indigenous communities as a way of promoting wellness. It is indeed evident that public schools are extending its effort to be of service to the local indigenous communities through significant economic, health, and community resilience initiatives.

Lastly, environmental stewardship pertains to the main drivers' efforts to apprise the indigenous communities of sustainable practices, conservation efforts, and environmental education awareness. Several respondents said that they conduct training and seminars about sustainable development practices to ICC and support for the IPEd program. Few respondents also emphasize the support of local ICCs through attending meetings and seminars, engaging in ICC activities including community clean-up drive, and attending IPEd seminars relative to environmental sustainability and conservation practices. This would mean that public school are supporting the United Nation's sustainable development goals and the Department of Environment and Natural Resources' goals of protecting, conserving, and managing the environment and natural resources for the present and future generations.

Through the public schools' engagements and initiatives on diverse external engagements and initiatives, the local indigenous communities have been capacitated as they extend culturally relevant information to the learners of Eskaya and the whole Eskaya indigenous cultural community. These results corroborate to the stances of Llego (2017) that public schools should establish school-community partnerships aimed at enriching the learning environment, as well as the community's engagement in the educative process. Also, the need for culture and identity preservation, have been the core of their significant efforts combined with the aspirations of the indigenous cultural community.

Table 2. Main Drivers of External Engagements and Initiatives

Themes	Codes
1. School principals/teachers/staff	Facilitate in the implementation of the external engagements and initiatives to the local indigenous communities
2. BLGU and MLGU	Participate and support in carrying out the external engagements and initiatives to the local indigenous communities
3. Other government and non-government agencies	Provide support, specifically on financial aspects, to sustain the conduct of external engagements and initiatives

Based on the relevant data provided by the respondents, the researcher has identified three themes on the main drivers in the external engagements and initiatives in supporting the Eskaya indigenous community. These are the school community members including school principals/teachers/staff, BLGU and MLGU, and other government and non-government agencies.

Firstly, majority of the respondents said that school principals, teachers and non-teaching staff are the main drivers of external engagements and initiatives. More importantly, several respondents also identified that the Barangay Local Government Unit, Municipal Local Government Unit and other government and non-government agencies take part in the implementation of the external engagements and initiatives. The aforementioned drivers have significant roles in delivering quality external engagement and initiatives to the indigenous cultural community.

With the identification of the main drivers of the external engagements and initiative, the researcher has investigated the essential contribution of school principals and teachers in the preservation of the Eskaya indigenous community. Significantly, the Eskaya elders and chieftain, as well as the BLGU, MLGU and non-government agencies, also served as relevant drivers in the success of the external engagements and initiatives undertaken by the IPEd implementing elementary schools. The researcher has seen that the success of programs lies in the positive collaboration and full support of all people and agencies involved. As reflected in the study of Dawson (2021), different forms of governance that influence conservation outcomes, paying particular attention to the role played by indigenous peoples and local communities represents the primary pathway to effective long-term conservation of culture and environmental resources.

Table 3. Challenges Encountered in the External Engagements and Initiatives

Themes	Codes
Financial constraint	It pertains to the budget allocation to carry out the plans and activities of the engagements and initiatives
Insufficient knowledge of the indigenous local community's language and cultural practices	Several drivers in the external engagements and initiative lack in-depth understanding of the culture and practices of indigenous local community
Unavailability of up-to-date technology-aided instructional materials	Less to no availability of technology-aided materials that would support in the implementation of the external engagements and initiatives to the local indigenous communities

The researcher has identified three themes on the challenges in the external engagements and initiatives of public schools in support to local indigenous communities. These are the financial constraint, insufficient knowledge of the indigenous local community's language and cultural practices, and unavailability of up-to-date technology-aided instructional materials. These three challenges are evident in most of the responses of the respondents. Based on the results, several of the respondents said that they do not have enough resources to contribute to the indigenous community and meet their needs; lack of funds for the LSA; lack of laws and policies and various quality higher education programs; and resources are often faced with limitations in funding, staffing and materials that hinder the implementation of specialized programs designed to support indigenous students. With these data, it is deemed important to revisit the funding allocation so as to provide adequate support to the learners and members of the indigenous community, Eskaya.

Furthermore, the researcher has also identified that insufficient knowledge of the indigenous local community's language and cultural practices is one of the challenges of the main drivers in the external engagements and initiatives in support of the indigenous community. To specify, several respondents said that teachers have limited knowledge on Eskaya language; some teachers cannot speak in Eskaya language; and lack of understanding and sensitivity towards indigenous cultures among school staff and non-indigenous learners that lead to miscommunication and misunderstanding. For the external engagements and initiatives to be fully realized and successful, the main drivers, specifically school principals and teachers, must be proficient in the use of Eskaya language and understanding of their cultural practices so as to avoid undesirable interpretations because of the lack of proficiency in using the Eskaya.

Lastly, few respondents have specified that unavailability of up-to-date technology-aided instructional materials in external engagements and initiatives is considered as a challenge of the main drivers. Particularly, respondents said that one of the ongoing challenges is the modernization and modern civilization of society because the objective of addressing preservation and nurturing the rich culture is being sacrificed. This would mean that with the advancement of technology in teaching and learning, it is also deemed relevant to upgrade the mode of teaching and learning in Eskaya in the local indigenous community without sacrificing their distinct culture, identity, and practices.

More importantly, a systematic review conducted by Diko (2023) underscored the historical component of indigenous identity and retainment strides, including challenges, that have been underlined in respect of South African indigenous cultural, language, and identity matters. Several challenges prevailed within the phenomenon in the South African context and must be acknowledged in a bid to solicit reasonable solutions to the problematized phenomenon. This is similar to this study as the main drivers have spelled out several challenges which the other governing organizations, public or private, may extend its help to further sustain the aspirations of the external engagements and initiatives to the local indigenous communities.

Based on the data collected in Table 5 on the next page, the researcher found three themes on the relevant needs of IPEd implementing elementary schools in sustaining the external engagements and initiatives of the local indigenous community. development of IP teachers, and teaching and learning instructional materials.

Table 4. Needs of Public Schools in Sustaining the Engagements and Initiatives

Themes	Codes
Financial support from BLGU and MLGU	It refers to the need of the external engagements and initiatives to collect monetary support from the local government units, barangay/municipal, to sustain the plans and activities for the local indigenous communities
Professional development of IP teachers	This implies that teachers, as one of the main drivers in the external engagements and initiatives, have to be capacitated with in-depth understanding of the indigenous local community's language and culture
Teaching and learning instructional materials	This refers to the need for integrating relevant and up-to-date technology aided teaching and learning materials

These are the economic support from BLGU/MLGU, professional. Firstly, as specified by the respondents, they need strong and full support from BLGU, MLGU, and Eskaya officials because it should start within their community before reaching the school level so that the school will find it easier to implement the external engagements and initiatives. Further, they added the insufficient budget, manpower, materials, support from LGU and IP elders. Some respondents also said that they need steadfast support of the project from other government and non-government agencies, and sufficient funding is crucial for developing and sustaining programs including hiring indigenous educators. With this data, it would mean that school principals and teachers need most the all-out economic support of BLGU and MLGU, to fully realize the intended external engagements and initiatives planned by the implementing elementary schools.

On the other hand, they also need professional development plans related to IPEd. To specify, several respondents said that they need permanent teachers who will teach the Eskaya language to perpetuate their Eskaya ILS/IKPS. Some respondents also added that as an IPEd implementing school, they need permanent teachers who will focus on the revival of culture and teach the Eskaya language. The respondents also said that they need professional development of teaches on cultural competency, indigenous histories and contemporary issues faced by indigenous communities to foster respectful and inclusive school learning environment. Based on these data, the main drivers of the external engagements and initiatives need IP teachers who will give focus and emphasis only on the Eskaya language acquisition and proficiency of the learners as the Eskaya language is only integrated across all subjects. Hence, they have seen the need to implement intensive emphasis on teaching the language itself to achieve Eskaya language proficiency. Also, they have expressed the need to further participate on relevant professional development relative to teaching indigenous cultural communities.

Lastly, the respondents have also expressed their needs for classroom and learning materials for their IP learners. Particularly, several respondents said that schools need to have classrooms intended solely for IP learners so that ILS and IKPs will be sustained. They also expressed that they need Eskaya learning materials and they need adequate funding resources that are directed towards progress and support indigenous education including technology and culturally relevant materials. This would mean that for the external engagements and initiatives to be sustained and successful, they need to have relevant learning materials and learning environment to aide in the instruction and realization of the indigenous knowledge systems and practices.

Findings

The study revealed the following findings:

- 1. External Engagements and Initiatives Undertaken by Public Schools:** Public schools have implemented various external engagements and initiatives in support of indigenous cultural communities. These include educational support, cultural

preservation and promotion, community development, and environmental stewardship. Each initiative is aimed at empowering indigenous communities and ensuring the sustainability of their cultural identity and environment.

- 2. Main Drivers and Collaborators of Engagements and Initiatives:** The primary drivers of these external engagements are the school principals, teachers, and staff who actively lead and facilitate the initiatives. In addition, strong collaborations with the Barangay Local Government Unit (BLGU), Municipal Local Government Unit (MLGU), and Non-Government Organizations (NGOs) play a vital role in the effective implementation and success of these programs.
- 3. Challenges in the Implementation of External Engagements:** Several challenges hinder the full execution of the initiatives. Among these are financial constraints, limited knowledge and understanding of the Eskaya language and cultural practices, and the lack of up-to-date, technology-aided instructional materials. These issues pose barriers to the continuity and effectiveness of school-led support for indigenous communities.
- 4. Expressed Needs to Reinforce External Engagements:** To strengthen external engagements and better support indigenous communities, there is an expressed need for financial assistance from BLGUs and MLGUs, ongoing professional development programs for Indigenous Peoples (IP) teachers, and the provision of technology-aided instructional materials tailored to the cultural context of the communities.

Conclusions

Significant efforts from the main drivers, particularly school principals, are clearly evident through their active involvement in external engagements and initiatives that align with the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads. These initiatives demonstrate their commitment not only to the academic development of learners but also to the cultural preservation of indigenous communities, particularly the Eskaya. Among the most pressing issues are the lack of financial support and the limited knowledge among teachers regarding the Eskaya language and traditional cultural practices. These challenges create barriers to delivering effective and culturally relevant instruction, making it difficult to fully implement and sustain programs that cater to the unique needs of indigenous learners.

To address these gaps, strong collaboration with both the Barangay and Municipal Local Government Units (BLGU and MLGU) is essential. These local government entities can provide crucial resources and policy support to help institutionalize and expand initiatives that support indigenous education. Additionally, partnerships with non-government organizations, community elders, and other stakeholders can enhance the delivery of culturally appropriate educational content and provide teachers with the necessary training and materials. The full support and active participation of all persons involved in these engagements are key factors in ensuring the continuity and success of

these initiatives. Collectively, their efforts have made significant contributions toward sustaining and enriching the distinct culture, identity, language, and traditional practices of the Eskaya indigenous cultural community, thereby promoting a more inclusive and responsive educational environment.

Recommendations

Considering the salient findings of the study, the following are hereby recommended by the researchers.

- 1. Extension of Financial Support to External Engagements and Initiatives:** Local government units and non-government agencies are encouraged to extend financial assistance to public schools in support of their external engagements and initiatives. These resources can help sustain programs and projects dedicated to the educational and cultural development of local indigenous communities. By strengthening financial backing, schools can better implement community-focused interventions and outreach efforts.
- 2. Professional Development for IP Education Implementation:** The Department of Education is advised to organize and deliver relevant, up-to-date training and workshops for school heads and teachers on Indigenous Peoples Education (IPEd). These capacity-building efforts should focus on cultural sensitivity, inclusive education strategies, and community engagement practices. Equipping educators with proper knowledge and skills will enhance the implementation and impact of programs aimed at supporting indigenous learners and preserving cultural identity.
- 3. Collaboration for Provision of Technology-Aided Instructional Materials:** Local government units, government agencies, and non-government organizations are encouraged to collaborate in supplying technology-aided instructional materials for learners in indigenous communities. These materials, tailored to the cultural and educational needs of IP learners, will enhance academic engagement and learning outcomes. The provision of digital tools and culturally responsive content will bridge learning gaps and foster inclusive education.
- 4. Expansion of Research on Indigenous Cultural Communities (ICCs):** Future researchers are encouraged to broaden the scope of their studies by including more respondents from local populations within and across areas inhabited by other Indigenous Cultural Communities (ICCs). This expanded coverage will allow for a more comprehensive understanding of cultural dynamics, educational needs, and the effectiveness of community-based initiatives. Comparative research across multiple ICCs can also generate policy-relevant insights and guide localized educational planning.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Before the conduct of the study, the researcher ensured that all ethical protocols were properly observed. Permission and informed consent were secured from the school administrators, who affixed their signatures to signify their voluntary agreement to participate as respondents. The researcher emphasized adherence to the basic principles of ethical research, such as anonymity, confidentiality, and voluntary participation. All participants were clearly informed of their rights and the objectives of the study, including their right to withdraw from participation at any time. Proper data management and the utmost confidentiality of the gathered information were assured throughout the research process.

To further ensure the integrity of the research, the study underwent an integrity test and citation audit. This process verified that the content of the study was original and free from plagiarism, reinforcing the credibility of the researcher's work.

The respondents of the study were fully informed that participation was purely voluntary. They were given the freedom to withdraw or decline at any point, whether due to health issues, discomfort with the topics discussed, or personal reasons. It was clearly communicated that their decision to participate or not would have no bearing on their previous, current, or future work-related status.

The researcher also clarified that no compensation or payment would be provided for participation. All responses were treated with an adequate level of confidentiality, handled respectfully, and protected with full privacy. The researcher ensured that the participants had a thorough understanding of the Informed Consent Form before proceeding with the study. The entire research process was conducted with transparency, integrity, and strict compliance with the approved research protocol, including the review and clearance issued by the Research Ethics Committee.

A Proposed Action Plan to Capacitate the Existing External Engagements and Initiatives of Public Schools in Support of Eskaya Indigenous Cultural Community

Rationale

Governments around the world take proactive stance on preserving all languages, especially ethnic languages, all efforts related to this, will help protect and promote linguistic diversity, intellectual diversity, cultural diversity and cultural identity. In fact, the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP) regenerated the rights of Indigenous People, which covers the declaration's scope, applicability, and implication on national law on indigenous rights (Mansell, 2011; Newcomb, 2011; Wiessner, 2008).

The distinctiveness of Eskaya has been a representation of the indigenous cultural community alliance and collaboration, although at present a low level of fluency of the language and preservation of the cultural practices among the community members is evident. Understanding the essence in the existence of their culture and uniqueness, dedicated members of the community make a conscious effort to revitalize the maintenance of their identity and set in motion the passion of preserving it.

After conducting the study and analyzing the results, it is revealed that there is a need to strengthen the collaboration with the Eskaya elders and chieftain and BLGU/MLGU to fully realize the external engagements and initiative undertaken by the school principals and teachers. Based on the identified challenges and needs from the respondents, the researcher sees the need to create an action plan capacitating the existing external engagements and initiatives to fully support the preservation of Eskaya indigenous cultural community.

Project Description

The action plan is a two-year round activity which focuses on calibrating the existing external engagements and initiatives using various interventions and collaboration with the concerned government agencies. Furthermore, there will be a project evaluation at the end of this two-year plan.

Project Objectives

The proposed project is geared towards the following objectives:

1. Review, revise, and improve the existing external engagements and initiatives;
2. Determine possible external funding to address the identified challenges and needs in the implementation of the external engagements and initiatives;
3. Enrich the teachers with sufficient learning materials that will aid in learning Eskaya language; and
4. Capacitate the IP teachers of Eskaya language and provide honorarium for the Eskaya elders for the time and effort they have extended to the indigenous community.

Project Detail

The matrix that follows presents the areas of concern, objectives, strategies to be employed and other details in the action plan.

Matrix

Areas of Concern	Objectives	Strategies	Persons Involved	Time Frame	Success Indicator
1. Result dissemination	To inform the Eskaya-ICC council, Local Barangay Unit and Local Government with the challenges and needs of the existing external engagement and initiatives	Conduct meeting and open forum	School principals and teachers Eskaya council BLGU/MLGU NGOs	Last week of September 2024	Awareness of the result of the study.
2. Revisit the existing external engagements and initiatives	To revisit the existing external engagement and initiatives to strengthen its implementation based on the identified challenges and needs	Consultation and open forum	School principals and teachers Eskaya council BLGU/MLGU	Last week of November 2024	Finalization of the revised copy of list of external engagements and initiatives
3. Seek support from the BLGU/MLGU and other government/non-government agencies	To present the challenges and needs of the existing external engagement and initiative to obtain sufficient funds from varied agencies	Conduct forum with the Eskaya-ICC council and concerned agencies for support in the engagements and initiatives	School principals and teachers Eskaya council BLGU/MLGU NGOs	First week of March 2025	Finalization of the MOU/MOA with the identified agencies to support the Eskaya indigenous community
4. Impact assessment	To evaluate the efficiency of the action plan.	Conduct open forum with the school principals and teachers, Eskaya-ICC council and agencies under MOU on matters regarding the efficiency of the action plan.	School principals and teachers Selected Learners Eskaya officials External Agencies under MOU	First week of December 2025	Smooth implementation of the said action plan.

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